

Brexit: An in-depth analysis of the Economic Implications the 2016 EU Referendum had on the United Kingdom

Abstract

The decision to leave the European Union has created several economic implications for the UK, and as such this paper aims to contribute to the Brexit literature by analysing Brexit's multifaceted impacts on the UK economy. The paper does this by conducting a counterfactual analysis to understand how the UK could have performed had it chosen to remain in the EU. Adopting such an approach gives us a yardstick to measuring the magnitude Brexit has had on the UK economy and its citizens. The findings of this analysis will also undergo thorough scrutiny to ensure the results presented are both plausible and valid. Through this evaluation, it becomes evident that Brexit has exerted adverse effects on the UK economy.

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1. Introduction

Brexit, a term that most people are tired of hearing, is associated with the decision made in June 2016, for the United Kingdom to part ways with the European Union (EU). This came to fruition after the UK said farewell to the EU Customs Union and Single Market on the 31st December 2020. In its departure, the UK managed to agree on a free trade agreement with the EU, whereby both parties will ‘not implement any tariffs or quotas on the movement of goods that are produced between the UK and the EU’ (Gov.uk, 2020). The decision to leave the EU has presented the UK with opportunities and challenges, and its economic implications are still subject to intense scrutiny and debate by leading academics.

The objective of this paper is to examine the various impacts that Brexit has had on the UK economy, from shifts in investment patterns, trade dynamics, and productivity levels, to movements in migration. Furthermore, this study will attempt to quantify the impact Brexit has had on the UK economy and evaluate whether or not it has improved household wealth.

Following the referendum results, substantial uncertainty regarding the economic implications of Brexit emerged, prompting numerous studies to explore and estimate its potential impacts under different Brexit deal scenarios, on the UK economy. Now, more than three years after formally leaving the EU with a free trade deal, Brexit-related literature has developed significantly, presenting updated and presumably more accurate results of its implications. This paper will therefore critically evaluate the recent literature published on Brexit, assessing the plausibility of its results. Delving into the latest research will also provide initial insights into the consequences that have unfolded since the UK departed from the EU.

It should be noted that analysing the effects of Brexit is presented with some challenges, notably in the fact that the outbreak of the pandemic has made it increasingly difficult to pinpoint the exact effects that are caused by Brexit from the ones caused by the pandemic. In response to this challenge, a counterfactual analysis has been conducted, to observe what the UK’s GDP growth rate path could have looked like if the UK had voted to remain within the EU. By undertaking a counterfactual analysis, it will attempt to isolate the effects attributable to Brexit, thus shedding light on Brexit’s impact on the UK economy.

To construct such a hypothetical scenario, the Synthetic Control Method will be employed. This method uses economic growth indicators from economies similar to the UK, to construct a ‘doppelganger’ that effectively mirrors the economic characteristics of a UK that remains within the EU.

The counterfactual analysis will help explore what were the short-term impacts of the EU referendum results on the UK economy. Specifically, it aims to dissect the effects stemming from the uncertainty surrounding the negotiation of a deal between the UK and the EU. Furthermore, the counterfactual analysis extends its examination to also understand the immediate consequences that have unfolded post-Brexit, such as the changes in trade dynamics with the EU and shifts in migration patterns in the UK.

Given the hypothetical nature of this analysis, it is essential to ensure that the results obtained are both plausible and reliable. Therefore, in the concluding sections of the paper, the results will be thoroughly scrutinised and compared to credible studies to assess their validity.

2. Literature Review

The prevailing consensus among academics regarding Brexit is that it has adversely impacted the UK economy, through shifts in trade dynamics, movements in migration, changes in investment spending, and heightening levels of economic uncertainty. It is important to note that this does not imply that academics do not believe Brexit has created any benefits; rather, academics suggest that the overall magnitude of the costs of Brexit tends to outweigh its advantages.

Thus, this section of the paper will delve into the extensive literature on Brexit and examine both Brexit's costs and benefits to the UK economy. This includes exploring studies that have employed a counterfactual analysis to estimate the costs of Brexit and analysing research conducted by the Office for Budget Responsibility (OBR).

2.1 Brexit Costs

The apparent costs of Brexit in the literature, stem from the elevated levels of uncertainty created by Brexit, the decline in trade integration with the EU and the implementation of more restrictive policies on migration. In this section, the paper will explore the contributions in the Brexit literature that specialise in these specific areas.

2.1.1 Changes in Trade Dynamics

The UK managed to successfully secure a free trade deal with the EU, but the decision to leave the EU Customs Union introduced a series of challenges for trade, as now 'there are customs checks at the border and goods will have to satisfy rules of origin requirements to qualify for

tariff-free entry’ (Huang et al, 2019). As a result, non-tariff barriers have risen since the UK withdrew from the EU leading to a rise in trade costs for both entities.

It is widely acknowledged that ‘trade integration can enhance productivity by promoting efficiency through increased competition, by stimulating innovation or by reducing the cost of intermediate goods’ (Huang et al, 2019). But with non-tariff barriers having risen, the cost of imports and exports between the UK and EU have subsequently risen, which resulted in a decline in the demand for exports and imports leading to a decline in trade integration and thus a potential fall in UK productivity. Evidence of the decline in trade dynamics of goods between the UK and EU is highlighted in *Figure 2.1*. While ‘imports have recovered to pre-pandemic levels, exports remain below 2019 levels in real terms’ (Ward & Webb, 2023).

Figure 2.1

(Ward & Webb, 2023)

Furthermore, Kern and Lawless (2024, p16) discover that ‘following the pandemic, the EU faced strong growth in imports and export trade with the rest of the world. In contrast, UK export trade to non-EU markets has experienced much slower growth in the aftermath of the pandemic, whilst UK imports from the rest of the world increased considerably.’ This finding seems reasonable, considering the UK would find it more challenging to obtain inputs from the EU, because of the rise in non-tariff barriers, consequently leading to a fall in the production of goods destined for non-EU markets, and thus a fall in output levels. *Figure 2.2* further

reinforces Kern and Lawless’s observation, by highlighting how the UK’s export volumes and trade intensity levels have been weaker than that of its global competitors. Therefore, Brexit has also led the UK to miss out on a supposed ‘boom’ in exports following the pandemic, which has adversely impacted the UK’s GDP levels.

Figure 2.2 – UK and advanced economy trade

(OBR, 2022)

Nevertheless, the UK’s withdrawal from the EU has also provided the UK an opportunity to negotiate trade deals independently and reduce its dependence on a single trading bloc, which could prove beneficial for the UK. However, the OBR revealed that ‘new trade deals agreed with non-EU countries has not had a material impact, as the deals concluded to date either replicate deals that the UK already benefited from as an EU member state, or do not have a material impact on the OBR’s forecast’ (OBR, 2023).

Upon reviewing the literature regarding trade between the UK and the EU thus far, it seems that remaining in the EU could have been more favourable for the UK. But by leaving the EU, trade integration with the UK’s ‘biggest trading partner’ has reduced, adversely impacting UK trade dynamics with both EU and non-EU markets. Therefore, withdrawing from the EU has seemingly harmed the UK’s trade dynamics and productivity levels.

2.1.2 Migration Movements

Brexit also marked the conclusion of the freedom of movement for EU nationals entering the UK, introducing potential implications for both the UK labour market and its economic growth. A key provision of the new system implemented stipulates that ‘new migrants should be coming to work in a job paying more than £25,600’ (Portes, 2022), thereby establishing a more uniform immigration system for both EU and non-EU nationals.

According to Sargent (2023, pg10), the new system could result in the UK suffering from lower productivity levels due to the closure of borders, skill shortages and less job competition. She also suggests that the case for Brexit cannot rest on economic rationale as her results suggest a ‘large decrease in workers’ wealth due to Brexit’ (2023, pg10).

In another study, ‘the Home Office estimated that under the new immigration system, there will be a reduction of 200 – 400,000 in net EU migration by 2025, partly offset by an increase of 40 – 100,000 in non-EU migration and that this will cause a small reduction in GDP (below 0.5 per cent)’ (Portes, 2022).

However, the impact assessment undertaken by the Home Office appears implausible, given that there has been a sharp increase (around 600,000 (*Figure 2.3*)) in the net migration of non-EU nationals since the introduction of the new immigration system. While there may be accuracy in the Home Office’s assertion about the decline in net migration of EU nationals, the significant underestimation of net migration among non-EU nationals cast doubts on the reliability of their impact assessment. Therefore, it is hard to draw any meaningful inference from the Home Office’s impact assessment and that movements in migration post-Brexit may not harm the UK labour market or economy, as previously thought.

Figure 2.3 - Provisional Estimates of UK Net Migration

(ONS, 2023)

As observed in *Figure 2.3*, there has been an unanticipated increase in net migration of non-EU nationals. The understanding behind this phenomenon, according to the ONS (2023), is that there has been a notable rise in the number of work and study-related visas awarded to

dependents from India and Nigeria since 2022. Moreover, the ONS claims that the war in Ukraine also played a crucial role in the surge since many Ukrainians had fled to the UK in search of safety and humanitarian aid. The breakdown of the surge is depicted in *Figure 2.4*, which highlights a considerable rise in the number of migrants arriving in the UK from 2019 to 2022 for humanitarian, educational and employment-related purposes.

Figure 2.4 – Reasons for the surge in net migration (2019-2023)

(ONS, 2023)

The existing literature on the effects of immigration caused by Brexit, suggests it would have had a small adverse effect on the UK economy. This argument could have been substantiated if there was a decline in the net migration of EU nationals coupled with no significant changes in the net migration of non-EU nationals. However, as this is not the observed trend, and that academics have underestimated the rise in net migration of non-EU nationals, implies that the effects of the changes in migration on the UK economy are unclear. Due to this ambiguity, this paper will seek to shed light on the potential implications that the overall rise in net migration will have on the UK, which has thus far received limited attention in the existing literature.

2.1.3 Brexit-related Uncertainty

Another consequence that the Brexit vote had, was that it unleashed an unprecedented amount of uncertainty, impacting the UK and EU macroeconomic landscapes. The surge in uncertainty, as noted by Makrychoriti and Spyrou (2022), has had far-reaching implications, dampening business and consumer confidence and capital outflows among others.

Figure 2.5 – UK Economic Policy Uncertainty

(Makrychoriti & Spyrou, 2022)

Figure 2.5 highlights how the uncertainty generated by Brexit surpassed that of even the global financial crisis. Such unprecedented levels of uncertainty led businesses in the UK to either postpone investments or relocate operations to more stable environments, such as those within the EU, thus, adversely impacting the UK economic environment. Makrychoriti and Spyrou's (2022) research supports this notion, revealing that 'prolonged uncertainty surrounding Brexit had positive effects on major EU countries and negative effects on the UK economy.' They were able to infer this by using Qual VAR modelling 'to build a continuous latent uncertainty variable that captures the propensity to Brexit uncertainty from a set of macroeconomic and financial variables' (Makrychoriti & Spyrou, 2022).

Moreover, corroborating studies in the literature that used different modelling techniques also arrived at the same conclusion, which strengthens the argument that the aftermath of the EU referendum had harmed the UK economy by creating an outlook of uncertainty.

2.2 Potential Brexit Benefits

While Brexit may appear predominately negative from an economic standpoint, the literature suggests that there are a few modest benefits, which will be discussed in this section of the paper.

2.2.1 EU Regulations

A notable benefit of Brexit is that the UK is no longer constrained by EU Regulations and can now tailor its regulatory framework to attract foreign investments. An impact assessment conducted by the 'UK government, identified that the costs of 56 regulations derived from EU legislation outweigh its benefits. The cost of these regulations amounts to 0.9% of the UK's GDP' (CEP, 2016). Therefore, the departure from the EU can be seen as beneficial as it provides the UK with the opportunity to reduce regulatory costs and implement regulations that can potentially make it a more appealing destination for investments, so long as potential investors do not want to trade with the EU.

2.2.2 EU Net Contributions

Another benefit is that prior to the UK's exit from the EU, the UK made financial contributions to the EU budget, and, in turn, received funding from the EU for various initiatives. However, because the UK was wealthier than some but not all of the EU members, the UK typically contributed more than it received from the EU budget. This can be highlighted during the transition period, where the UK made a 'gross contribution of £17 billion to the EU budget but only received £4.5 billion from the EU, therefore making a net contribution of £12.6 billion' (Keep, 2022). Whilst this might seem insignificant given the UK's economic size, it still presents an opportunity for the UK to now redirect these 'EU net contributions' towards improving public services such as the NHS.

2.3 Counterfactual Analysis

Evaluating the immediate impacts of withdrawing from the EU became more challenging due to the outbreak of the pandemic. The reasoning behind this is that the pandemic caused significant disruptions to migration patterns, trade relations and consumer and investment spending. Therefore, making it more difficult to pinpoint the exact effects that stem from Brexit and not the pandemic. Had the pandemic not occurred, comparing the effects of Brexit on the UK with global counterparts like France and Germany might've been more straightforward.

However, considering how the pandemic would have impacted each country differently, conducting a comparative analysis may be deemed ineffective.

Nonetheless, undertaking a counterfactual analysis can isolate the effects that Brexit has had on the UK. Such analysis can be used to compare observed outcomes with a hypothetical scenario, specifically one where the UK voted to remain within the EU. Creating such a scenario involves constructing a synthetic entity, often referred to as a “doppelganger”, that replicates the economic growth path of the UK from 2009 (post-financial crisis) to when the EU Referendum took place in 2016. This doppelganger is created by using a composite of various developed economies carefully selected.

Once the doppelganger is constructed, it serves as a tool to predict what the UK’s real GDP growth path might have looked like had the UK remained in the EU. Thus, creating such a hypothetical scenario gives us a yardstick to measuring the damage inflicted by Brexit.

Therefore, considering how this paper has employed a counterfactual analysis to examine the economic implications of Brexit, it is imperative to review previous research and investigate studies that have also used one. In doing so, it will provide insightful information for understanding the process of creating a UK doppelganger and the counterfactuals explored will also serve as a baseline for comparing the results obtained from this study.

2.3.1 Synthetic Control Method

One such analysis was conducted by John Springford. Springford used a technique known as the Synthetic Control Method (SCM) to construct a UK doppelganger. In the initial phase of his approach, Springford focused on training the algorithm to ‘minimise differences between the UK and 22 other advanced economies across specific economic indicators (such as economic growth, investment and trade levels) during the designated training period (Q1 2009 to Q4 2011)’ (Springford, 2022a).

In the next step, he programmes the algorithm to minimise the differences in the growth rate of real GDP between Q1 2012 and Q2 2016. To reduce the dependence of the algorithm on any one country, Springford ‘repeatedly ran the model on donor pools from which countries have been randomly dropped. He ran the model on a donor pool of 5, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15, 18, 20 and 22 countries’ (Springford, 2022a). Therefore, his approach aims to generate a counterfactual that possesses economic characteristics similar to the UK, whilst also helping to mitigate the risk of over-reliance on any single country.

By using the SCM, Springford was able to project the doppelgänger’s real GDP growth path from Q2 2016 to Q2 2022 and discovered that the UK’s real GDP growth path was ‘5.5% lower than the doppelgänger’ (Springford, 2022b) which amounts to a £33 billion shortfall:

Figure 2.6 – SCM UK Doppelgänger GDP Growth Path

(Springford, 2022b)

However, Gudgin and Lu (2023, p7) criticised Springford’s estimated impact arguing that it does not provide a credible measure of the cost of Brexit since the countries used for the doppelgänger are ‘not significantly related in the statistical sense to GDP growth in the UK.’ For example, the inclusion of economies like Greece and Iceland in the SCM is questionable despite both having distinctive experiences of economic growth post-financial crisis and that their economic structure differs significantly from that of the UK. This implies that the doppelgänger’s GDP growth path post-2016 may be misleading and that Springford’s cost of Brexit is possibly inaccurate.

2.3.2 Error Correction Method

Due to the weaknesses noted in Springford’s approach, Gudgin and Lu (2023, p10) proposed an alternative counterfactual analysis which used countries that are statistically significantly related to the UK, i.e. USA, Germany, and Switzerland. They used a conventional regression equation known as the Error Correction Method (ECM) which used ‘quarterly changes in UK

GDP as a dependent variable, and both levels and changes in independent variables (which estimate long-term and short-term influences)’.

The results reported were similar to those reported by Springford, as depicted in *Figure 2.7*. However, by using fewer variables, and making the model more transparent, Gudgin and Lu were able to discover that the main reason for the divergence between the doppelganger and the UK, was because the US was driving the counterfactual. ‘The reason for the USA’s superior performance since 2016 is because US fiscal policy has been more expansionary than the UK’s under both the Trump and Biden administrations’ (Gudgin & Lu, 2023, p12).

Figure 2.7 – GDP volume index with 2009Q1=100, UK vs ECM forecast

(Gudgin & Lu, 2023)

Although, one criticism of Gudgin and Lu’s approach centres around the limited sample size they used, which causes the US to become the dominant driver in shaping the counterfactual. Expanding the dataset to include more economies that exhibit statistical correlation with the UK economy, could potentially mitigate the over-reliance on the US and still produce similar results.

In both counterfactual analyses that have been observed, both studies generate a counterfactual that has a higher GDP level than the UK before the emergence of the pandemic which is quite plausible. The reasoning behind this is that this difference could be attributed to the impact of Brexit-related uncertainty, which led businesses to adopt a more cautious stance towards

investing in the UK, causing the UK economy to grow more slowly than its doppelganger. Therefore, Gudgin and Lu should not dismiss other plausible factors that contribute to the disparities in the counterfactual analysis by simply stating that the US is driving the counterfactual.

So far, identifiable weaknesses have been highlighted in the counterfactual analysis approaches undertaken by Springford and Gudgin and Lu. Nevertheless, constructing a UK doppelganger can offer valuable insights, provided that any differences between the doppelganger and observed outcomes are carefully explained. Thus, the counterfactual analysis undertaken in this paper will strive to address the shortcomings witnessed and thoroughly explain any disparities observed. In doing so, it will provide a more robust and transparent assessment of the economic implications of Brexit.

2.4 Office for Budget Responsibility's Brexit Analysis

A huge headline came in 2023 from the Office for Budget Responsibility (OBR) suggesting that 'the post-Brexit trading relationship between the UK and the EU, will reduce long-run productivity by 4 per cent relative to remaining in the EU.' This largely reflects OBR's 'view that the increase in non-tariff barriers on UK-EU trade acts as an additional impediment to the exploitation of comparative advantage.'

Furthermore, the OBR estimated that 'around two-fifths of the 4 per cent impact had already occurred by the time the Term and Cooperation Agreement (TCA) came into force, as a result of uncertainty weighing on investment and capital deepening' (OBR, 2023).

The OBR obtained these results by averaging the cost of Brexit from various studies that each used different modelling techniques to calculate the possible impact that would be caused by Brexit if the UK agreed on a Free Trade Agreement (FTA) deal with the EU. The studies selected are shown in the chart below:

Chart A

Table A: Long-run effect on productivity of trading with EU on FTA terms

Organisation	Model	Productivity assumption	Per cent Effect
Felbermayr et al (2018)	New quantitative trade model	Constant returns to scale	-1.8
IMF (2018)	Computable general equilibrium	Constant returns to scale	-2
Mayer et al (2018)	New quantitative trade model	Constant returns to scale	-2.4
UK in a Changing Europe (2019)	New quantitative trade model	Constant returns to scale	-2.5
OECD (2016)	NIGEM	Dynamic productivity	-2.7
IMF (2018)	Computable general equilibrium	Melitz-style increasing returns to scale	-3.3
Netherlands CPB (2016)	Computable general equilibrium	Krugman-style increasing returns to scale	-3.4
Bank of England (2019)	Gravity modelling	Dynamic productivity	-3.5
NIESR (2018)	Gravity modelling	Dynamic productivity	-3.8
Whitehall Study (2018)	Computable general equilibrium	Melitz-style increasing returns to scale	-4.9
UK in a Changing Europe (2019)	Gravity modelling	Dynamic productivity	-6.4
Netherlands CPB (2016)	Computable general equilibrium	Dynamic productivity	-5.9
World Bank (2017)	Gravity modelling	Dynamic productivity	-10
Average			-4.0

(OBR, 2020)

The approach undertaken by the OBR is questionable, as most of these studies, whilst credible at the time it was published, do not account for the evolving dynamics leading up to Brexit, especially with the emergence of the pandemic and the rise in Brexit-related uncertainty.

While the OBR did appropriately select studies that calculated the cost of Brexit under FTA terms, most of them primarily focused on how trade dynamics would impact productivity, neglecting other crucial factors like movements in migration and the rise in uncertainty levels. Consequently, as some of these studies solely focus on what the effects of the changes in trade dynamics will have on the UK economy, it potentially underestimates the actual impact of Brexit.

Therefore, the OBR estimate should be approached with a degree of caution, and the impact of Brexit could potentially be more significant than the indicated 4%. Nevertheless, what can be confidently inferred from the research conducted by the OBR, is that there is a consensus that changes in trade dynamics caused by Brexit have adversely impacted the UK economy, but the precise magnitude of Brexit's impact remains up for debate.

2.5 Productivity Puzzle

Before the EU referendum took place, the UK had experienced an ‘unusual flat lining of productivity since 2010’ (ONS, 2015), which seemed unprecedented as the historic trend of productivity in the post-war era has been upward. This productivity puzzle is highlighted below:

Figure 2.8 – UK Productivity (1997 - 2015)

(ONS, 2015)

This stagnation in productivity had caused the UK to lag behind ‘other major developed economies and is often attributed to relatively low levels of investment in the UK’ (ONS, 2015):

Figure 2.9 – Difference from UK productivity level, G7 countries, 2013

(ONS, 2015)

Before the EU referendum, the UK was struggling with the challenge of enhancing its productivity levels and was trailing behind its global competitors. It is worth noting that UK productivity has been a complex issue since the global financial crisis, and its complexity will be mentioned later in the paper when understanding if Brexit has affected productivity. However, if the results in this paper achieve similar results to those of the OBR, Brexit would have worsened a longstanding issue for the UK.

3. The Model

The emergence of the pandemic has undoubtedly complicated efforts to identify the effects attributable to Brexit. However, as demonstrated in the literature review, one approach to overcome this challenge and isolate the effects of Brexit is by conducting a counterfactual analysis.

As such, this paper will build upon the groundwork laid by Springford's counterfactual analysis and will address any criticism that was directed at his work. One such criticism was that the majority of the 22 economies' real GDP growth selected by Springford to construct the doppelganger was not 'statistically significantly correlated with the UK over the 2009Q1 – 2016Q2 period' (Gudgin & Lu, 2023, p7). Gudgin and Lu asserted that the lack of statistical correlation undermines the meaningfulness of the results drawn from Springford's approach.

Gudgin and Lu also performed their own counterfactual analysis and achieved similar results to Springford. However, an argument for their approach was that the US was the main driver of the counterfactual, which meant that the doppelganger's economic growth was excessively high and, thus, seemed implausible to them. The over-reliance on the US in Gudgin and Lu's approach may have stemmed from the limited sample size they used.

Therefore, to not repeat the mistakes observed, this paper aims to construct a counterfactual with reduced reliance on the US by expanding Gudgin and Lu's sample size to include more countries that exhibit statistical correlation with the UK economy. By doing so the counterfactual analysis conducted in this paper strives to generate a more accurate and reliable measure of the cost of Brexit.

3.1 Country Selection

3.1.1 Pearson Correlation Test

In order to address the criticism of Springford's approach, this study will conduct a Pearson Correlation test to discover which economies are statistically significantly correlated to the UK's real GDP growth path from 2009Q1-2016Q2. This ensures that when the algorithm is constructing the counterfactual, it is only considering economies that experienced similar growth rates to the UK. In doing so, it prevents countries that have similar economic characteristics to the UK but very different growth rate experiences from being selected which can improve the accuracy of the counterfactual analysis.

The following Hypothesis was formed:

$$H_0: \text{the true correlation between the UK and a country} = 0$$

$$H_1: \text{the true correlation between the UK and a country} > 0$$

The Hypothesis test was conducted on developed EU economies, Canada, Japan, Norway, and the US, as they are recognised as suitable comparators with the UK. It should be noted that countries like Australia, Greece, Iceland, and New Zealand were excluded due to being distinctly dissimilar to the UK.

(Further details on where the real GDP growth rates (%) were collected can be found in Appendix 3.1.)

3.1.2 Pearson Correlation Results

The null hypothesis was rejected at the 1% significance level for the following countries:

- Austria
- Denmark
- Japan
- Switzerland
- Belgium
- France
- Netherlands
- Sweden
- Canada
- Germany
- Norway
- United States

Note: all the countries above exhibit a strong positive correlation with the UK's real GDP growth path from 2009Q1 to 2016Q2. (See Appendix 3.2 for further details)

There was insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis at the 1% significance level for countries like Italy, Portugal, and Spain, as they all experienced weak recovery from the global financial crisis. These countries had been included in Springford's approach which could reduce the statistical inference derived from his results.

Thus, through the Pearson Correlation Test, 12 economies are found to be statistically significantly correlated to the UK economy from 2009 Q1 – 2016 Q2. This sample size is greater than that used by Gudgin and Lu and can help reduce the reliance on any one country to dominate the doppelganger.

3.2 Synthetic Control Method

Having selected the countries to construct the UK doppelganger that hypothetically voted to remain in the EU in 2016, the SCM will be employed. This method was first introduced by Abadie et al (2012) where they analysed what effects the German Reunification had on West Germany's GDP levels. Their explanation of how the SCM works was that 'the comparison unit (doppelganger) in the synthetic control method is selected as the weighted average of all potential comparison units that best resembles the characteristics of the case of interest (West Germany)'. The characteristics Abadie et al (2012) used to construct the West Germany counterfactual were a set of economic growth predictors:

- Real GDP per Capita
- Inflation Rate
- Industry Share of Value-Added
- Schooling
- Measure of Trade Openness

Springford used a similar approach for constructing the UK doppelganger. This study will likewise use the same approach but with some adjustments.

The first step of the SCM entails training the model to replicate the UK's real GDP growth path from 2009 Q1, shortly after the global financial crisis, to 2016 Q2, just before the EU Referendum. A strong fit with the observed growth path during this stage will instil confidence that the doppelganger can accurately represent a UK that remains part of the EU.

In the training period, the SCM will aim to minimise the differences between the UK and the selected countries chosen across specific economic indicators from 2009 Q1 to 2011 Q4. This will help ensure the counterfactual constructed best resembles the UK economy. The economic indicators used are as follows:

- **Quarterly Real GDP growth rate:** ensures the counterfactual's real GDP growth path aligns closely with that of the UK that is an EU member state
- **Inflation Rate (CPI):** Selecting economies with inflation rates similar to the UK for the doppelganger is crucial, as it indicates that the economies selected adopt a similar monetary policy stance as the UK does in certain macroeconomic environments. For instance, Japan's monetary stance is quite distinct from the UK's, having implemented a negative bank rate following the global financial crisis. This has led to Japan experiencing negative/low inflation rates, a situation not mirrored in the UK. Hence the SCM will consider this and assign a lower weight to Japan, creating a doppelganger whose monetary policy stance is similar to the UK's.
- **Gross Fixed Capital Formations (% of GDP):** Is a crucial economic indicator that influences an economy's economic development. The SCM will therefore select economies that have a similar investment share as the UK.
- **General Government Deficit:** This variable was added in response to Gudgin and Lu's (2023, p6) criticism of Springford's approach for not including data on government budget deficits, as government spending can heavily influence an economy's output level. By adding this variable, the SCM will look to apply weights to economies that adopt fiscal policy measures similar to what the UK adopts in response to certain macroeconomic shocks.
- **Measure of Trade Openness (Exports plus Imports of both goods and services as a % of GDP):** The SCM will avoid applying weights to countries that rely significantly more/less on international trade than the UK does.
- **Employment Rate:** the SCM will favour countries that have similar labour market experiences to that of the UK.

The data on the economic growth indicators was collected from the OECD (*Appendix 3.3*). It should be noted that the Industry Share of Value Added is not included as the OECD had no data on the Gross Value Added (GVA) of Industrial activities on the US and is thus excluded in this approach. This does reduce the accuracy of the counterfactual but to a small extent. The variables used are still sufficient to create a counterfactual that best resembles that of the UK which has voted to remain in the EU.

In the next step, the algorithm is programmed to specifically minimise the differences in the economic growth rates among the selected countries from 2012 Q1 - 2016 Q2. Once this stage is completed, the algorithm will then produce a set of weights with the sample size used, to

replicate the UK's economic growth path from 2009 Q1 to 2016 Q2. If a strong fit is demonstrated, the algorithm can then proceed to project the doppelganger's GDP growth path up to 2023 Q3 with the set of weights calculated in the training period.

To mitigate the risk of any single country dominating the doppelganger, the SCM is repeated using different sample sizes. It initially begins with a sample size comprising 20% of the population, randomly selecting three out of twelve countries to construct a new counterfactual. Then it increases the sample size to 30%, 40%, and so forth until the entire sample is used. This results in the creation of nine counterfactuals, each created by a different sample size. The final step involves averaging these counterfactuals to formulate the UK doppelganger as follows:

Figure 3.1

The counterfactual constructed demonstrates a strong fit with the UK real GDP data from 2009 Q1 to 2016 Q2. This alignment instils confidence in the doppelganger's ability to accurately depict the growth path of a UK economy that has hypothetically remained within the EU post-2016. By constructing the doppelganger in this way, it can be inferred that any disparities between its growth path and that of the UK are attributable to Brexit, thus providing a credible way to quantify the impact Brexit has had on the UK economy.

3.4 Limitations

It should be acknowledged that the counterfactual analysis conducted does come with its limitations. One such limitation is the inability of the counterfactual analysis to forecast the long-term costs of Brexit, primarily due to the unavailability of real GDP data beyond 2023 Q3.

Another notable limitation arises from the substantial weight allocation assigned to the US, which could cause the counterfactuals' growth path to be excessively high, as seen in Gudgin and Lu's counterfactual analysis. The weight allocation of the doppelganger is depicted in Chart B:

Chart B

Country	Weight Allocation
United States	0.41
Denmark	0.21
Canada	0.15
Netherlands	0.15
Switzerland	0.08

In Springford's approach, the counterfactual assigned a weight of 31% to the US, which is lower than the weight allocated in this paper. The difference in weight allocation can be attributed to differences in sample size, as this study uses a smaller sample size in comparison to Springford. The rationale behind opting for a smaller size in this study is a deliberate decision aimed at excluding economies that exhibit distinct dissimilarities with the UK. Springford's inclusion of such dissimilar economies may reduce the weight assigned to the US, but it makes it harder to draw any statistical inference from his results. Thus, allocating a larger weight to the US, in order to draw statistical inference from the results is a risk worth taking.

3.4.1 Why does the US dominate the UK doppelganger?

Despite the considerable disparity in the sizes of the UK and US economies, both economies exhibit striking similarities on a relative scale. This becomes particularly noticeable when examining the historical GDP growth trends between the two countries, as the UK's and US' GDP growth trends are parallel from 1990 to 2016, and even begin to grow at the same rate in the aftermath of the global financial crisis. After viewing such similarities, it is no surprise why the US does get assigned a large weight allocation in the counterfactual.

Figure 3.2

(Appendix 3.1)

Although the weight allocation of the US in the counterfactual is lower than that in the Gudgin and Lu counterfactual, a critical assessment in the next section of this study is warranted to determine if disparities in the UK and its doppelganger can be attributed to Brexit or whether the disparities are caused by the US being the primary driver of the counterfactual.

4. Results

The counterfactual generated indicates that Brexit has resulted in the UK's GDP level being 5.5% lower than had it remained within the EU as of 2023 Q3, which is roughly in line with Springford's result. In monetary terms, this translates to a £124 billion decline in GDP which is significantly different to Springford's shortfall of £33 billion. The understanding behind this is simple, Springford uses quarterly GDP volume data, where if you add up each quarter's GDP level in a year, it will equal the size of the UK economy. Hence if you add the differences in Springford's doppelganger and what was observed for each quarter in 2022, Springford's cost of Brexit will roughly equate to £130 billion, aligning closely to the findings in this paper. Whilst this paper adopts a much simpler method, as the GDP volume data used has been annualised so that any divergences between the doppelganger and the UK are equal to the cost of Brexit:

Figure 4.1

(Appendix 4.1)

In this section, a critical assessment will be conducted to determine the plausibility of the results and identify the economic implications Brexit has had on the UK economy. The most effective approach in doing this involves breaking down the results into three sections: one focused on examining the short-term effects of the Brexit vote (2016-2020), one section on understanding why the pandemic affected the UK less in the hypothetical scenario and the other dedicated to analysing the immediate effects of departing the single market (2021 onwards).

4.1 What were the short-term effects of the Brexit vote?

The counterfactual analysis indicates that before the emergence of the pandemic, the results of the EU referendum had caused a 1.4% reduction in the UK's real GDP level. This decline can be linked to the uncertainty created by the referendum result because the possibility of leaving the EU was initially thought to have damaging economic implications for the UK.

The economic/political uncertainty sparked by the vote led to an immediate reaction in financial markets, resulting in the pound depreciating rapidly against both the US dollar (by 8%) and the euro (by 7%):

Figure 4.2

(Appendix 4.2)

Typically, when a country's currency depreciates, its exports become relatively cheaper, leading to a rise in demand for its exports whilst its imports become relatively more expensive, reducing demand for imports. As a result, firms purchasing imported goods are expected to incur higher costs, which may result in higher prices being charged to their consumers.

Although there is 'no evidence finding that Brexit reduced UK's trade with the EU' before 2020 (Freeman et al, 2022), Dhingra and Sampson's (2022) findings do discover that 'the rise in inflation from 0.5% on June 2016 to 3.1% November 2017 was caused by the fall in the sterling'. Therefore, the UK voting to leave the EU led to the depreciation of the pound which subsequently led to the rise in inflation and the cost of living in the UK.

A depreciating pound was the first observed implication stemming from Brexit-related uncertainty. Over time, Brexit-related uncertainty intensified further, as depicted in *Figure 4.3*, which highlights there was an increasing proportion of firms citing Brexit as a significant source of uncertainty:

Figure 4.3

(Bank of England, 2019)

As illustrated in the chart, Brexit-related uncertainty saw a notable surge in 2018, which coincides with the divergence in the counterfactual analysis. The Bank of England (2019) revealed that due to this observed trend in Brexit-related uncertainty, UK business investment had stagnated, as the cumulative growth of investment spending from 2016 to 2019 amounted to around 0.4%. The understanding behind this is that firms are forward-looking and that the UK macroeconomic outlook was becoming increasingly uncertain due to Brexit, causing UK firms to become reluctant to make any investment decisions. UK firms therefore delayed their investments which contributed significantly to the observed stagnation.

By delaying investment decisions, firms would have also foregone the benefits stemming from new investment projects. It also meant the levels of expenditures on capital and research and development could have been significantly higher in the absence of Brexit-related uncertainty. This, in turn, indicates that the Brexit vote ultimately led to a decline in capital, resulting in

firms producing less output causing UK productivity to worsen, which would thus adversely affect the UK's economic growth.

This line of reasoning finds support in the findings of the Bank of England, which discovered that business investment could have been remarkably higher had the UK voted to remain in the EU:

Figure 4.4

(Bank of England, 2019)

In the absence of Brexit-related uncertainty, a higher level of business investment would have likely been attained, which could have fuelled greater expansion in the UK's productive capacity, ultimately driving up output growth following the EU referendum results. Therefore, it is plausible to suggest that Brexit-related uncertainty contributed to a 1.4% decline in the UK's real GDP levels.

This reported decline closely aligns with the OBR's estimate of a 1.6% decrease in the UK's long-run productivity attributed to Brexit-related uncertainty, which reinforces further confidence in the results drawn upon from the counterfactual analysis and that it is justifiable to expect the UK doppelganger to experience higher economic growth in the short-term aftermath of the EU referendum.

4.2 Why did the pandemic affect the doppelganger less than it did with the UK?

With the short-term impacts of Brexit, derived from the counterfactual analysis, being deemed valid, focus has shifted towards understanding why the doppelganger experienced a lower rate of decline in GDP compared to what was observed during the pandemic. This result is questionable because, irrespective of Brexit, it is reasonable to assume that the UK would have implemented similar lockdown measures in response to the challenges posed by the pandemic. Hence, one would expect the doppelganger to have mirrored the rate of decline in GDP as observed in 2020.

It can be argued that the absence of a UK-EU agreement until the 24th December 2020 increased uncertainty levels for UK households and businesses who were concerned about the possibility of a no-deal scenario occurring. The rise in uncertainty would have resulted in further delays in consumption and investment decisions, whilst also causing UK businesses to spend excessively in planning for a no-deal scenario. This would have undoubtedly had adverse effects on the UK's economic growth. Thus, had the UK voted to remain, it might have indeed experienced a smaller decline in growth during the pandemic than what was observed.

However, the counterfactual analysis indicates that Brexit-related uncertainty led to the cost of Brexit rising significantly, from 1.4% in 2019 Q4 to 9% in 2020 Q4. This is highly improbable and that this 'jump' in the cost of Brexit is likely influenced by external factors, which casts doubts around the reliability of the counterfactual results projected from 2020 onwards.

The reason for the doppelganger performing significantly better than what was observed during the pandemic period is not hard to find. It mainly arises from a limitation in the counterfactual analysis whereby the countries used to construct the UK doppelganger all faced less severe economic consequences than the UK had during the pandemic. The OBR (2021) explains that the 'UK had endured higher rates of infection, hospitalisations, and deaths from the pandemic than other countries,' leading to more prolonged periods of strict lockdowns, consequently exerting a more adverse impact on the UK economy.

Although the counterfactual provides insightful information about how a UK that remained within the EU would have responded to specific economic events, it falls short in accounting for the unique nature of the pandemic. Unlike a typical economic crisis, the pandemic was

primarily a health crisis, which led each country to experience varying impacts between one another. Therefore, it causes the counterfactual analysis to underestimate the impact of the pandemic on the doppelganger, and thus causes the results post-2020 Q2 to be less reliable.

Whilst the counterfactual has attempted to isolate the effects of Brexit, it becomes apparent that the growing difference between the doppelganger and what has been observed in 2020 is largely attributable to the pandemic and not Brexit. Springford’s and Gudgin and Lu’s counterfactual analysis also suffers from the same underlying issue which they fail to account for, causing their results to be less reliable as well. To address this issue, the counterfactual presented will now grow at the same rate as the UK did from the outbreak of the pandemic (2020 Q2) to the easing of lockdown restrictions (2021 Q2). While this adjustment entails sacrificing some of the immediate effects of officially leaving the EU, it is a crucial modification to prevent the results of the counterfactual analysis from appearing implausible. The modifications made produced the following results:

Figure 4.5

Having adjusted the doppelganger to incorporate the real GDP growth rates that were observed between 2020 Q2 to 2021 Q2, Brexit is understood to have caused a 3.4% decline in the UK GDP levels as of 2023 Q3. This equates to a £73 billion decline in the GDP level and has made households approximately £1074 worse off. This result deviates from Springford’s

findings as expected, but closely aligns with estimates from the National Institute of Economic and Social Research (NIESR). According to their counterfactual analysis, the NIESR (2023) discovered that ‘3 years after the end of the transition period, UK real GDP is 2-3% lower than what it would have been had the United Kingdom retained its EU membership. This corresponds to a reduction of around £850 per capita as of 2023.’ Their results are outlined below:

Figure 4.6

(NIESR, 2023)

Whilst the approach taken by the NIESR to generate their counterfactual was different to that used in this paper, its close alignment between their counterfactual analysis and the one conducted in this paper reinforces confidence in the accuracy and validity of the results derived from each study. Therefore, with the results of the adjusted counterfactual analysis closely aligning with that of a reputable institution, attention can now be directed towards understanding what the immediate effects of leaving the EU were.

4.3 What were the economic implications of officially leaving the EU?

The UK officially leaving the EU in 2021 meant the UK departed from the EU Single Market and the EU Customs Union, creating various economic implications for the UK economy. The counterfactual analysis conducted highlights that the difference between the doppelganger and the UK grew larger post-2021 Q1, suggesting that the official departure from the EU, adversely

impacted the UK economy. In this section, the immediate effects of departing the EU will be explored to understand if the discrepancy in the counterfactual analysis post-2021, is plausible.

4.3.1 Change in Trade Dynamics

Before the UK departed from the EU, the TCA was established. The TCA ensures the continuation of tariff- and quota-free trade in all goods and incorporates certain provisions for services. However, immediately after the UK left the EU, ‘businesses – both exporters and importers – faced higher trade costs due to more stringent customs checks’ (NIESR, 2023). These increased expenses in trade have caused firms in both the UK and EU to scale back their trade activities with one another. This is supported by Dhingra and De Lyon (2021) who found from a survey they conducted that 24% of firms reported that Brexit had caused exports to the EU to fall, while 33% of firms noted a reduction in imports from the EU.

Further evidence of the decline in trade integration between the UK and EU is made evident in *Figure 4.7*, where it is highlighted that shortly after the transition period ended, there was a sharp decline in both imports and exports between the UK and the EU.

Figure 4.7

(Appendix 4.3)

Although exports eventually rebounded to pre-Brexit levels by the end of 2021, and imports recovered shortly after, there remains a possibility that, without Brexit, the UK could have experienced more robust growth in its exports post-2020. This conjecture stems from the

observation that the UK's growth in exports lagged behind that of other advanced economies, as it faced a sharp decline in goods trade in 2021 from leaving the EU:

Figure 4.8 – Goods Exports

(Deloitte)

While Brexit has noticeably affected the UK's trade in goods, the situation appears different for trade in services, which seemingly remained unchanged following the conclusion of the transition period.

Figure 4.9

(Appendix 4.3)

The evidence observed indicates that whilst trade in services has largely been unaffected by Brexit, the rise in trade costs stemming from Brexit has adversely affected the UK's trade of goods, more specifically its exports. Another implication of the rise in trade costs, arising from Brexit, is its contribution to the surge in inflation witnessed in recent years, as businesses facing higher costs from imports have passed these expenses onto their consumers, by raising consumer prices.

Dhingra and De Lyon (2021) support this notion as they revealed that 33% of firms reported in a survey they conducted, that Brexit increased their businesses cost, prompting them to raise prices for UK consumers. Furthermore, research from Batter et. al (2022), showed that Brexit has caused food prices to rise by 6%, placing a substantial £5.8 billion burden on UK consumers. Such rises in consumer prices have undoubtedly affected lower-income families the most, who are already struggling in the cost-of-living crisis. Therefore, Brexit has helped fuel the surge in inflation, with its impact mostly felt by households with low incomes, thereby widening the gap between social classes.

The rise in trade barriers has also impacted financial markets in the UK as it's now become more costly to invest in the UK. This became apparent in 2021, with over '440 firms in the banking and finance sector' leaving the UK within one year of its departure from the EU (NIESR, 2023). With the UK now being rendered a less appealing destination for investments, it is reasonable to infer that Brexit has further reduced investment spending in the UK and its capital stock, leading to output and productivity levels being lower than had the UK remained within the EU.

As the changes in non-tariff barriers continue to develop, it becomes increasingly apparent that the UK has become a less appealing destination for investments than had it remained within the EU. Furthermore, Brexit appears to have played a substantial role in driving up inflation, as well as causing the UK to lag behind other advanced economies in terms of growth in exports. While the long-term trade implications continue to develop, it is evident that in the absence of the rise in trade costs, the UK could have experienced stronger growth in its exports of goods, lower levels of inflation and higher levels of investment and output. Thus, it appears plausible that if the UK had remained in the EU, it could have achieved higher GDP levels than what has been observed, thereby validating the 3.4% decline in real GDP levels that is attributable to Brexit.

4.3.2 Changes in Migration

The conclusion of the transition period also marked the end of the freedom of movement for EU nationals entering the UK. In its wake, the UK has implemented a new point-based immigration system where ‘new migrants arriving in the UK must work in a job paying more than £25,600’ (Portes, 2022). This system not only ensures uniform treatment for all migrants, irrespective of their EU or non-EU status but also emphasises a strategic focus on attracting skilled individuals to the UK.

Under this new immigration system, it was anticipated that there would be a decline in overall net migration in the UK following Brexit. However, contrary to these expectations, overall net migration has surprisingly surged since the UK departed from the EU Single Market, as depicted below:

Figure 4.10

(ONS, 2023)

The increase in overall net migration can be largely attributed to the influx of non-EU nationals. The first reason for this influx of non-EU nationals is that the departure of EU nationals due to Brexit left vacancies in the labour market, prompting the need for non-EU workers to fill this gap. The second reason is that the introduction of new visa routes, notably the ‘‘Skilled Worker’’ visa and the ‘‘Graduate’’ visa (ONS, 2023), has facilitated easier entry for non-EU nationals,

particularly from countries like India and Nigeria to migrate to the UK. This influx of non-EU migrants has likely attracted highly skilled/qualified individuals to pursue opportunities in the UK.

Theoretically, under the new immigration system, more skilled workers should be entering the UK now than had the UK remained within the EU. This should mean that the overall skill composition of the UK labour market should have increased after the transition period ended, potentially increasing efficiency and innovation levels in various UK industries. Consequently, one might expect the recent migration movements to positively impact the UK’s productivity levels, suggesting that Brexit hasn’t overwhelmingly been negative.

However, despite these expectations, the UK’s productivity levels have stagnated since the second quarter of 2021. This is depicted in *Figure 4.11*, where it is shown that the number of employees in the UK labour market grew from the influx of skilled migrants, whilst the UK’s productivity levels remained largely unchanged. This implies that the influx of non-EU nationals has not translated into immediate economic benefits for the UK. However, it’s crucial to acknowledge the complexity of the UK’s productivity levels, as highlighted in the literature review, particularly since the UK’s productivity levels have stagnated since the global financial crisis. Thus, implying that factors beyond the skill level of the workforce play a significant role in shaping productivity levels in the UK.

Figure 4.11

(Appendix 4.4)

While the current analysis of changes in migration is simplistic, it does suggest that the recent movements in migration have not had a material impact on the UK economy, thus far. Therefore, it is reasonable to assert that, as of now, the UK's departure from the EU has not yielded any clear and immediate benefits to the UK economy.

4.4 Are there any Brexit benefits?

Considering the absence of economic advantages stemming from the new immigration system in the UK, a critical inquiry arises: Have there been any Brexit Dividends? Advocates for Brexit have contended the UK's reliance on the EU Single Market and the ability to independently negotiate new trade deals would prove advantageous for the UK. However, as stated by the OBR (2023) new trade deals with non-EU countries have either replicated trade deals the UK would have benefited as an EU member state or do not have a material impact on the UK economy.

Another presumed benefit of Brexit was the ability to no longer financially contribute to the EU budget. Yet, findings from the NIESR (2023) suggest the 'impact of the reduction in the UK net contribution to the EU is negligible.' With no evident advantages emerging from the departure from the EU, advocates of Brexit have noted that if Brexit has adversely affected the UK economy, why has the UK outperformed the 3 biggest EU economies since 2016?

While a comparative analysis depicted in *Figure 4.12* reveals that the UK did experience greater growth than France, Germany, and Italy post-referendum, it does not necessarily negate the impact of Brexit on the UK economy. This is why conducting a counterfactual analysis was imperative to comprehending the referendum's short- and medium-term effects, as well as quantifying the damage inflicted by Brexit on the UK economy, which a comparative analysis would have dismissed.

Figure 4.12

(Appendix 3.1)

Hence, whilst the UK did experience better economic performance than its European counterparts after the referendum, it is essential to acknowledge that the UK could have grown, by more than 3.4% (or £73 billion), if the decision to leave the EU had not been made.

Therefore, after scrutinizing the apparent Brexit benefits and understanding that their impact on the UK has been negligible, it is evident that voting to leave the EU has adversely impacted the UK economy and that the UK doppelganger experiencing stronger growth than what was observed is a plausible and valid result.

5. Conclusion

To conclude, the impact of Brexit on the UK economy remains complex and ongoing, and as such, this paper refrains from making long-term predictions of the cost of Brexit. Despite Brexit having an ongoing impact, observable effects of Brexit already indicate that Brexit has harmed the UK economy. The counterfactual analysis conducted in this paper estimates that if the UK had opted to remain in the EU, its GDP level would be 3.4% higher as of 2023 Q3, reflecting a substantial loss of £73 billion attributed to Brexit, making household £1074 worse off.

The results derived from the counterfactual analysis are deemed valid and reliable, as plausible explanations accounting for instances where the doppelganger experienced stronger economic growth than the UK were made. Furthermore, the results from the counterfactual analysis align

closely with the OBR's analysis of Brexit and the counterfactual analysis conducted by the NIESR (2023). Thus, the results derived in the paper are deemed plausible and reliable.

The adverse impact of Brexit on the UK can be broken down into two parts: the short-term repercussions of the referendum results and the immediate consequences of withdrawing from the EU:

The immediate aftermath of the referendum results saw the pound depreciate against both the dollar and the euro, leading to an increase in UK inflation. The referendum results also gave rise to both political and economic uncertainty which prompted businesses in the UK to stall their investments. By stalling investments, UK investment levels had stagnated which adversely impacted the UK's output levels, leading to a 1.4% reduction in the UK's GDP levels by 2020.

Upon reaching an agreement with the EU, Brexit-related uncertainty fell. However, by leaving the EU Customs Union it meant businesses importing and exporting from the EU faced higher trade costs due to the rise in non-tariff barriers which led to the UK experiencing both higher rates of inflation and weaker growth in its exports. It also made the UK a less appealing destination for investments, which further harmed the UK's productivity levels. In the absence of Brexit, higher levels of investments could have been attained, which could have increased capital levels, and thus boosted UK output levels. The implication of this is significant as the UK's GDP levels could have been 3.4% higher by the end of 2023 had the UK voted to remain.

Given these considerations, there appears to be a lack of economic rationale justifying the withdrawal from the EU. While it is understood that Brexit could potentially yield long-term benefits, its current implications have been associated with increasing inflation, weakening the pound, stagnation in investment levels, weak export growth, and an overall decline in the country's output and productivity levels. Whilst political benefits for Brexit may exist, the decision to leave the EU has led the UK economy to experience a loss of £73 billion in GDP levels.

Appendix

3.1 Data on the Real GDP Growth rates was collected from the OECD Data Explorer website (from 2008 Q4 to 2023 Q3):

OECD Data Explorer. 2024. *Quarterly real GDP growth – OECD countries* [Online]. OECD Data Explorer. Available from: [https://data-explorer.oecd.org/vis?df\[ds\]=dsDisseminateFinalDMZ&df\[id\]=DSD_NAMAIN1%40DF_QNA_EXPENDITURE_GROWTH_OECD&df\[ag\]=OECD.SDD.NAD&df\[vs\]=1.0&pd=2009-Q1%2C2023-Q4&dq=Q..SWE%2BPOL%2BNOR%2BJPN%2BDNK%2BAUT%2BPRT%2BUSA%2BGBR%2BCHE%2BESP%2BNLD%2BKOR%2BITA%2BDEU%2BFRA%2BCAN%2BBEL.S1..B1GQ.....G1.&ly\[rw\]=REF_AREA&ly\[cl\]=TIME_PERIOD&to\[TIME_PERIOD\]=false&vw=tb](https://data-explorer.oecd.org/vis?df[ds]=dsDisseminateFinalDMZ&df[id]=DSD_NAMAIN1%40DF_QNA_EXPENDITURE_GROWTH_OECD&df[ag]=OECD.SDD.NAD&df[vs]=1.0&pd=2009-Q1%2C2023-Q4&dq=Q..SWE%2BPOL%2BNOR%2BJPN%2BDNK%2BAUT%2BPRT%2BUSA%2BGBR%2BCHE%2BESP%2BNLD%2BKOR%2BITA%2BDEU%2BFRA%2BCAN%2BBEL.S1..B1GQ.....G1.&ly[rw]=REF_AREA&ly[cl]=TIME_PERIOD&to[TIME_PERIOD]=false&vw=tb) [Accessed 31 January 2024]

3.2 Pearson Correlation Results (how correlated were a country's real growth GDP to that of the UK's):

Country	Correlation	p-value	Null Hypothesis
Austria	0.9022303	4.869e-12	Rejected
Belgium	0.9688431	< 2.2e-16	Rejected
Canada	0.9648391	< 2.2e-16	Rejected
Denmark	0.9722307	< 2.2e-16	Rejected
France	0.9497559	5.878e-16	Rejected
Germany	0.9365961	1.406e-14	Rejected
Italy	-0.5987998	0.9998	Accepted
Japan	0.9177891	4.745e-13	Rejected
Netherlands	0.8883364	2.864e-11	Rejected
Norway	0.9705191	2.2e-16	Rejected
Poland	0.9797691	2.2e-16	Rejected
Portugal	-0.4923617	0.9971	Accepted
Spain	0.01036783	0.4783	Rejected
Sweden	0.9597993	< 2.2e-16	Rejected
Switzerland	0.9846727	< 2.2e-16	Rejected
United States	0.9947779	< 2.2e-16	Rejected

3.3 Economic Growth Indicators were collected from the OECD database (from 2008 Q4 to 2023 Q3):

The data on GFCF, Exports and Imports was collected from here:

OECD Data Explorer. 2024. *Quarterly GDP and components – expenditure approach, US Dollars* [Online]. OECD Data Explorer. Available from: [https://data-explorer.oecd.org/vis?df\[ds\]=dsDisseminateFinalDMZ&df\[id\]=DSD_NAMAIN1%40DF_QNA_EXPENDITURE_USD&df\[ag\]=OECD.SDD.NAD&df\[vs\]=1.0&pd=2009-Q1%2C2023-Q4&dq=Q..USA%2BGBR%2BESP%2BNLD%2BIRL%2BDEU%2BFRA%2BCAN%2BBEL.S1..P7%2BP6%2BP51G%2BB1GQ.....LR..&ly\[rw\]=REF_AREA&ly\[cl\]=TIME_PERIOD&ly\[rs\]=TRANSACTION&to\[TIME_PERIOD\]=false&vw=tb](https://data-explorer.oecd.org/vis?df[ds]=dsDisseminateFinalDMZ&df[id]=DSD_NAMAIN1%40DF_QNA_EXPENDITURE_USD&df[ag]=OECD.SDD.NAD&df[vs]=1.0&pd=2009-Q1%2C2023-Q4&dq=Q..USA%2BGBR%2BESP%2BNLD%2BIRL%2BDEU%2BFRA%2BCAN%2BBEL.S1..P7%2BP6%2BP51G%2BB1GQ.....LR..&ly[rw]=REF_AREA&ly[cl]=TIME_PERIOD&ly[rs]=TRANSACTION&to[TIME_PERIOD]=false&vw=tb) [Accessed 31 January 2024]

Data on CPI inflation:

OECD Data. 2024. *Inflation (CPI)* [Online]. OECD Data. Available from: <https://data.oecd.org/price/inflation-cpi.htm> [Accessed 31 January 2024]

Data on Employment Rates:

OECD Data. 2024. *Employment rate* [Online]. OECD Data. Available from: <https://data.oecd.org/emp/employment-rate.htm> [Accessed 31 January 2024]

Data on General Government Deficits:

OECD Data. 2024. *General Government Deficit* [Online]. OECD Data. Available from: <https://data.oecd.org/gga/general-government-deficit.htm> [Accessed 31 January 2024]

4.1 UK GDP volume data was collected from the OECD Data Explorer, which was used to construct *Figure 4.1*. Data was Calendar and Seasonally Adjusted, Data was also transformed to Annual levels:

OECD Data Explorer. 2024. *Quarterly National Accounts (for 'Developer API')* [Online]. OECD Data Explorer Available from: [https://data-explorer.oecd.org/vis?df\[ds\]=dsDisseminateFinalDMZ&df\[id\]=DSD_NAMAIN1%40DF_QNA&df\[ag\]=OECD.SDD.NAD&df\[vs\]=1.0&pd=2008-Q4%2C2023-Q4&dq=Q.Y.GBR...B1GQ.....LR.LA.&ly\[cl\]=TIME_PERIOD&to\[TIME_PERIOD\]=false&vw=tb](https://data-explorer.oecd.org/vis?df[ds]=dsDisseminateFinalDMZ&df[id]=DSD_NAMAIN1%40DF_QNA&df[ag]=OECD.SDD.NAD&df[vs]=1.0&pd=2008-Q4%2C2023-Q4&dq=Q.Y.GBR...B1GQ.....LR.LA.&ly[cl]=TIME_PERIOD&to[TIME_PERIOD]=false&vw=tb) [Accessed 4 April 2024]

4.2 Data on the Pound/Euro and Pound/US Dollar was collected from Yahoo Finance from 2016 to 2020 (weekly data):

Yahoo Finance. 2024. *GBP/EUR (GBPEUR=X)* [Online]. Yahoo Finance. Available from: <https://uk.finance.yahoo.com/quote/GBPEUR%3DX/history?period1=1451606400&period2=1577836800&interval=1d&filter=history&frequency=1d&includeAdjustedClose=true> [Accessed 4 April 2024]

Yahoo Finance. 2024. *GBP/USD (GBPUSD=X)* [Online]. Yahoo Finance. Available from: <https://uk.finance.yahoo.com/quote/GBPEUR%3DX/history?period1=1451606400&period2=1577836800&interval=1d&filter=history&frequency=1d&includeAdjustedClose=true> [Accessed 4 April 2024]

4.3 Data on UK Imports and Exports Monthly Volume was collected for the Office of National Statistics:

Office for National Statistics. 2023. *UK trade: December 2023* [Online]. Office for National Statistics. Available from: <https://www.ons.gov.uk/economy/nationalaccounts/balanceofpayments/bulletins/uktrade/december2023> [Accessed 4 March 2024]

4.4 Data on the growth in Output per Work and in Employment was collected from the Office for National Statistics

Office for National Statistics. 2023. *Productivity flash estimate and overview, UK: October to December 2023 and July to September 2023* [Online]. Office for National Statistics. Available from:

<https://www.ons.gov.uk/employmentandlabourmarket/peopleinwork/labourproductivity/articles/ukproductivityintroduction/octobertodecember2023andjulytoseptember2023> [Accessed 4 March 2024]

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